

Reflections from demographic data of the world Muslim population

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ABSTRACT

Demographic data are essential to Islamic societies. The origins of a census are to be found in the first year of Islamic calendar ordered by the Prophet (pbuh). While the actual number of people populating earth is comparable to the supposed number of Muslims who ever lived on earth is at least interesting. Leaving the spiritual interpretation to the competent ones we could give based in 'semi-scientific data' an approximate of this number. Calculations show that from 1,07 billion people ever lived on earth 7,269,215,000 (6.8%) were born Muslims. Further elaboration of data represented graphically show the ever living Muslim population as proportion to the living at that point of time of other humans population which indicates some interesting *breaking points*. All data have to be taken in consideration carefully because of precarious sources of information.

INTRODUCTION

A Qur'an *surah* gave the Prophet (pbuh) and His community the glad tidings of a great victory as the conquest of Makah and the embracing of Islam in whole crowds.

- 1. When comes the victory of Allah, and the Conquest,**
- 2. And you see mankind entering the Religion of Allah in troops,**
- 3. So extol with the praise of your Lord, and ask Him forgiveness; surely He has (always) been Superbly Relenting.**

Qur'an; 110. Dr. Ghali translation.

A question of practical importance would be to know the number of the living Muslim population on earth and other demographic data. Another question could ask "how many Muslims ever lived on earth?" or "what is their proportion to other people who don't belong to Islam?" While concerns about demography are present from the time of Prophet (pbuh) who ordered the conduction of a census at the first year of the Islamic calendar the other questions remain of 'semi-scientific' value but interesting. [1]
Data usually are not of too much importance in the view of relationships' with other religious communities so long as coexistence and tolerance are based on the most high human values, meanwhile they can be important in more practical meters as in planning and forecasting for example, human resources.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The idea of this work came while, nowadays you can see estimates of humans population the earth from 50,000 B.C., although based in precarious data in the existence of man in earth, number of births and deaths and other possible biases.

We took the data on Muslim population from actual scientific demographic sources, while data on “births per 1,000” were adopted from a study which considers all human population, not just Muslims. The same method which was applied for all human population was adopted in our calculations except in the case of population data between benchmark years where we used the average of the upper and lower class limits for the population.

Graphical presentations for each of tabular findings are used in form of bubble and surface charts.

RESULTS

Results are focused in two main elements of calculations, the supposed number of all Muslims who ever lived on earth and their proportion to other living humans.

Tab. 1 Total number of Muslims ever lived on earth by year

Year	Population ^[1]	Births per 1,000 ^[2]	Births since previous date*	Cumulative**
600	0			
800	11,000,000	80		
1000	23,000,000	80	176,000,000	187,000,000
1100	32,000,000	80	220,000,000	407,000,000
1200	44,000,000	60	304,000,000	711,000,000
1300	52,000,000	60	288,000,000	999,000,000
1400	56,000,000	60	324,000,000	1,323,000,000
1500	71,000,000	60	381,000,000	1,704,000,000
1600	98,000,000	60	507,000,000	2,211,000,000
1700	114,000,000	50	636,000,000	2,847,000,000
1800	162,000,000	50	690,000,000	3,537,000,000
1850	215,000,000	40	471,250,000	4,008,250,000
1900	282,000,000	40	497,000,000	4,505,250,000
1950	478,000,000	38	760,000,000	5,265,250,000
1975	852,000,000	35	631,750,000	5,897,000,000
2000	1,290,000,000	31	937,125,000	6,834,125,000
2010	1,588,000,000	23	446,090,000	7,280,215,000
Total			7,269,215,000	

* Births since previous date, presumes the number of births considering referred birth rates and the average of the upper and lower class limits for the population column.

** Cumulative, adds-up actual population value to the previous cumulative time segment class.

Fig. 1 Number of Muslims ever lived on earth compared to all others

	Number	%
World Pop. 2011	6,215,000,000	
Nr. of people who ever lived	107,000,000,000	
Muslims who ever lived	7,269,215,000	6.8
Other	99,730,785,000	93.2

Tab. 2 Comparison between numbers of living humans in a point in time to the all supposed living Muslims till that time

Year	Other living*	Muslims' ever**
1200	406,000,000	711,000,000
1650***	402,000,000	2,211,000,000
1750	681,000,000	2,847,000,000
1850	1,050,000,000	4,008,250,000
1900	1,656,000,000	4,505,250,000
1950	2,038,000,000	5,265,250,000
1995	4,470,000,000	6,834,125,000
2011	4,627,000,000	7,280,215,000

* Number of supposed leaving human population in earth at the appointed year except Muslims.

** Number of supposed people labeled from birth as Muslims (ummah of Prophet Mohammad (pbuh). Other people are considered as Muslims from Qur'an but left out of this calculation. **"In no way was Ibrahim a Jew, neither a Christian; (i.e. a follower of Isa "Jesus", Nasraniyyan) but he was an unswervingly (upright) (i.e. veering away from idolatry) Muslim; and in no way was he one of the associators (Those who associate others with Allah)." Qur'an; 3:67.** Dr. Ghali translation.

*** Colored cells year are approximated to the two sources of information differing 50 years to each other.

Fig. 2 Comparison between numbers of other living humans in a point in time to the all supposed living Muslims till that time

DISCUSSION

While world population clock is ticking 7.6 billion people this study suggest some estimates for Muslim population ever lived on earth. The number 7,269,215,000, 2010 estimate represent the estimated number of Muslim population who ever lived on earth. The bubble chart shows the ever living Muslim population (little circle with Kaaba figure) to the total number of people ever lived on earth (big circle picturing world map). Second this calculation Islam holds 6.8% of all humans ever lived on earth for its followers. Other Muslims lived on earth but this data represent the *ummah* of Prophet Mohammad (pbuh). An interesting fact was the comparison of ever living Muslim in different points of time to the living humans in that point of time. The graphical presentations shows interesting breaking points in certain times which could orient for further examination in modes of Islam spread, for example, through conversion or increased birth rates and decreased number of deaths, especially infant deaths.

CONCLUSIONS

In this world and the other numbers matter. The above results must be considered '*semi-scientific*' as the referred author writes about his results. Lastly we calculated, in condition that if the number of people were the criteria of knowledge attainment, we could expect to have by year 2010;

144 persons like Imam Abu Hanifa (699 - 767 CE / 80 - 148 AH),
144 persons like Imam Malik ibn Anas (733 - 795 CE / 114 - 178 AH),
144 persons like Imam Al-Shafi'i (767 - 820 CE / 149 - 204 AH),
144 persons like Imam Ahmad ibn Hanbal (780 - 855 CE / 163 - 240 AH),
144 persons like Muhammad al-Bukhari (810 - 870 CE / 194 - 256 AH),
144 persons like Muslim ibn al-Hajjaj (815 - 875 CE / 199 - 261 AH),
69 persons like Al-Qushayri (986 - 1072 CE / 375 - 464 AH),
50 persons like Imam Al-Ghazali (1058 - 1111 CE / 448 - 504 AH),
36 persons like Ibn Arabi (1165 - 1240 CE / 560 - 638 AH),
36 persons like Jalal ad-Din Muhammad Rumī (1207 - 1273 CE / 603 - 671 AH),
31 persons like Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya (1292 - 1350 CE / 691 - 751 AH).

6542. Narrated Abu Hurairah (ra) : I heard Allah's Messenger (pbuh) saying, "From my followers there will enter Paradise [without (being asked about their accounts)] a group, seventy thousand in number, whose faces will shine as the moon does on a full moon night". On hearing that, 'Ukāsha bin Mihsan Al-Asdi got up, lifting his covering sheet, and said, "O Allah's Messenger! Invoke Allah that He may make me one of them." The Prophet (pbuh); said, "O Allah, make him one of

them." Another man from the Ansar got up and said, "O Allah's Messenger! Invoke Allah to make me one of them." The Prophet (pbuh) said (to him), "'Ukāsha has preceded you." [4]

Referring to this study conclusion we must be very careful because of serious possible biases from information sources used as are assumed birth rates, population estimates, etc. Assumptions of constant population growth could underestimate it in the earliest period, while an earlier date of the appearance of humans on earth would raise the number. [5]

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